

MANUFACTURING AND DESIGN OF INTERLOCKED COMPOSITE GRIDS

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SUMMARY: Composite grid structures made from pultruded unidirectional glass or carbon ribs provide unmatched performance/cost combination of any composite panels. A new manufacturing method for an ortho-grid using slotted joint and adhesive bonding has been developed. The high structural performance of the grid is derived from uni-ply and the efficient load transfer mechanism. Pultrusion is one of the cheapest, fastest and reliable manufacturing processes for composite sections. Pultruded ribs, along with the simple assembly concept, lead to the low cost structure. Equivalent stiffness model for a square grid has been developed. The equivalent plate stiffness matrices including the effect of the slots and the rib caps has been formulated. The equivalent stiffness model has been verified.

KEYWORDS: Interlocked Composite Grids, Pultrusion, Equivalent Stiffness

INTRODUCTION

The work presented here is part of Ph.D. dissertation at Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics at Stanford University [4].

Composite grids are unique. They capture the highest stiffness and strength of composites by keeping fiber directions along the ribs. Composite grids are also unique in utilizing the anisotropy of unidirectional plies. Higher anisotropy means higher translation of composite properties to grid properties. Unidirectional plies have unmatched mechanical properties when load is applied along the fiber axis. Other fiber architectures in laminated, woven, preform, and braided composites all suffer from lower properties because fibers are not straight and their fiber volume fractions are low. Typical fabric properties are compared with uni-ply in fig. 1 [1]. They are lower by factor of three or more.

Fig. 1 Stiffness and strength of uni-ply

At the same time, manufacturing costs of the conventional laminated composites are high because of the necessary cold storage, layup or weaving, tooling, bagging, curing, and assembly. The relative costs of various composite processes are shown in fig. 2 [2]. Other

processes such as RTM and VARTM can produce complex parts. However their performance is comparable to fabric composites having woven fibers and low fiber fractions. The drastic cost savings in the last two processes in the figure over layup processes are obvious. However, the low cost process such as pultrusion and filament winding have seen limited usage for highly loaded structures because of the lack of effective assembly and joining methods. The main objective of the study is to develop manufacturing and design methodologies of a composite grid structure that takes full advantages of the superior properties of the unidirectional composites and the low cost manufacturing processes.

Fig. 2 Cost comparison of various processes

The grid structures with unidirectional composite ribs offer several advantages over conventional structures. First, by using unidirectional ribs, all the fibers are aligned along the load path and the material properties are utilized most efficiently. Second, this type of structures is damage tolerant since a crack in one rib does not propagate to the next ribs. Third, grids have higher specific bending stiffness because you can build thicker structure for the given amount of material. Fourth, all the other usual benefits of composites, such as light weight and corrosion and fatigue resistance are retained.

MANUFACTURING

A new manufacturing method for square or rectangular flat grid panel using slotted joints and adhesive bonding has been developed. Starting components are pultruded unidirectional ribs and rib-caps. Slots are cut into the ribs. A square or rectangular grid is formed by inserting the matching slots into one another. Rib caps are then bonded to bridge the open slots and to provide an additional load path. The whole structure is interlocked as shown in fig. 3.

The main features of the proposed manufacturing and assembly concept include, first, the slotted joints facilitating the assembly and not requiring any special fixtures. Very large structures can be assembled on site, if required. Second, the ribs and caps are manufactured by pultrusion, which is the most reliable, fully automated, and the cheapest and fastest manufacturing process of composite sections. Pultrusion of unidirectional sections can achieve high fiber volume fraction of over 70%. This high performance is directly transferred to the performance of the grid. It provides unmatched performance/cost ratio of any composite panel. Third, the same concept can be extended to single curvature shell structures such as conical and cylindrical grids.

Fig. 3 Assembly of Interlocked Composite Grid (ICG)

Slots can be cut as the sections are pulled. Abrasive water-jet or synchronized saw blade can be combined with pultrusion. Alternatively, many ribs can be stacked and cut in one pass of a saw blade. Rib assembly is very easy and fast due to the slots and does not require special fixtures. Due to the simplicity of the steps, field assembly of large panels is possible, if required. Also, extremely large panels are possible since pultrusion can produce theoretically infinite lengths of sections. A picture of an ICG panel of 10 foot length, 10 foot width, and 6 inch height is shown in fig. 4. This is a remarkably large structure built by composites, but even larger panels are possible.

Fig. 4 10' x 10' x 6" ICG panel

STIFFNESS OF AN ICG

There are at least two different types of stiffness models that can be used to predict the global behavior of a grid. One is the "Exact Stiffness Model" where individual ribs, caps, and joints of a grid are simulated exactly. Generally, it requires large computational memory, time, and cost. Also, any changes during design process may require regeneration of all meshes. Hence, the exact stiffness model is very inefficient and not suitable for the design process. This has motivated the development of a simpler stiffness model, the "Equivalent Stiffness Model."

For a grid with enough number of cells, the equivalent stiffness model, where the rib properties are smeared into a homogenized equivalent plate, can accurately predict the global behavior of a grid. The equivalent stiffness model is simpler and more efficient, so is more suitable for design and optimization processes than the exact stiffness model. Particularly, it is

a very powerful tool for buckling and modal analyses where the solutions require number of iterations.

The stiffness of an ICG is reduced by the presence of the slots. To measure the stiffness reduction, two cap efficiency factors, in-plane and flexural, have been defined. The in-plane cap efficiency factor (eq. 1), e_o , indicates the stiffness reduction in tension or compression and is defined as the ratio of axial rigidity of slotted T-section beam to that of a solid T-section beam without slots. Similarly, the flexural cap efficiency factor (eq. 2), e_f , indicates the stiffness reduction in bending and is defined as the ratio of flexural rigidity of slotted to solid T-section beams. These factors range between 0 and 1 and are functions of L/h and R , where L is the distance between the slots, h is the rib height, and R is the area ratio of the cap to rib (fig. 5).

$$e_o = \frac{(EA)_{slot}}{(EA)_{solid}} = f\left(\frac{L}{h}, R\right) \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

$$e_f = \frac{(EI)_{slot}}{(EI)_{solid}} = f\left(\frac{L}{h}, R\right) \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

Fig. 5 Definition of the area ratio R

The axial rigidity of the slotted beam, $(EA)_{slot}$ in eq. 1, and the flexural rigidity of the slotted beam, $(EI)_{slot}$ in eq. 2, are calculated from finite element analysis. Beams with ten slots with different L/h and R are modeled, and the finite element mesh with symmetric boundary conditions is shown in fig. 6. The rigidities of solid T-beams without slots are calculated from simple beam analysis. Larger L/h results in higher values for the cap efficiency factor because larger slot spacing results in less slot interaction. Also, larger values for R results in higher values because the larger cap area provides more load path to go around the slots.

Fig. 6 Finite element mesh for slotted beams

In-plane and flexural cap efficiency factors as functions of L/h and R are shown in fig 7 and 8 for glass sections. L/h is varied from 0.33 to 5 and R from 0.1 to 1. The cap efficiency factors

increase as L/h and R increase as expected. The increment of the in-plane cap efficiency factor is gradual and the value ranges between 60 percent and 90 percent. Caps are more efficient for the recovery of bending stiffness as shown in fig. 8. For R greater than 0.5 and L/h greater than 1, the flexural cap efficiency factors are greater than 95 percent; the grids suffer little from the slots. In this range, the bending stiffness reduction due to the slots can be neglected. For carbon sections, the trend and the actual values of the cap efficiency factors are similar. The effects of slots on out-of-plane shear stiffness and torsional stiffness are neglected as they are small compared to the longitudinal and bending stiffness.

These factors are included in the formulation of the equivalent plate stiffness matrices of an ICG. Stiffness matrices of a square ICG are derived by considering the stiffness of a T-section beam (combination of rib and cap). Axial and bending rigidities of a T-section beam are calculated with respect to the neutral axis of the beam, and the cap efficiency factors are applied to account for the stiffness reductions due to the slots. It is assumed that the slots do not change the location of the neutral axis of the beam. The neutral axis planes of the T-beams in x direction and y direction do not coincide when they are assembled into an ICG. The mid-plane is chosen as a reference plane. The Parallel Axis Theorem [3] is used to calculate the axial and bending rigidities with respect to the mid-plane. The average force and moment resultants, and the stiffness of the equivalent plate are found. The neutral axis planes of x and y direction beams and the mid-plane are shown in fig. 9.

Fig. 9 Neutral axis planes and mid-planes of the T-beams in x and y directions

The distance between the neutral axis plane and the mid-plane in fig. 9 can be expressed in terms of the rib and cap dimensions as in eq. 3.

$$d = \frac{ct(h+t)}{2(bh+ct)} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

The corrected axial rigidity $(EA)^*$ and the bending rigidity $(EI)^*$ of the T-beam are shown in eq. 4, where the origin of z' axis is at the neutral axis plane. The in-plane and flexural cap efficiency factors are applied to account for the stiffness reduction due to the slots.

$$(EA)^* = e_o \int E dA = e_o E_{rib} (bh + ct)$$

$$(EI)^* = e_f \int E z'^2 dA = e_f E_{rib} \left(\frac{bh^3}{12} + bhd^2 + \frac{ct^3}{12} + ct \left(\frac{t}{2} + \frac{h}{2} - d \right)^2 \right) \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

The total axial forces and moments with respect to the neutral axis of the T-beams in x and y directions are

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{N}_x' &= (EA)^* \mathbf{e}_x' \\ \bar{N}_y' &= (EA)^* \mathbf{e}_y' \end{aligned} \quad (\text{Eq. 5})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{M}_x' &= (EI)^* k_x \\ \bar{M}_y' &= (EI)^* k_y \end{aligned} \quad (\text{Eq. 6})$$

Eq. 5 and 6 are rewritten in eq. 7 and 8 with respect to the mid-plane using the Parallel Axis Theorem [3]. Note that the direction of the offset from the mid-plane to the neutral axis is different for x and y direction beams as shown in fig. 9. There are coupling terms due to the caps.

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{N}_x &= (EA)^* \mathbf{e}_x^o + d(EA)^* \mathbf{k}_x \\ \bar{N}_y &= (EA)^* \mathbf{e}_y^o - d(EA)^* \mathbf{k}_y \end{aligned} \quad (\text{Eq. 7})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{M}_x &= d(EA)^* \mathbf{e}_x^o + \left((EI)^* + d^2 (EA)^* \right) \mathbf{k}_x \\ \bar{M}_y &= d(EA)^* \mathbf{e}_y^o + \left((EI)^* + d^2 (EA)^* \right) \mathbf{k}_y \end{aligned} \quad (\text{Eq. 8})$$

In equations 5 and 6, the prime superscript denotes quantities with respect to the neutral axis. The superscript “o” denotes quantities with respect to the mid-plane in equations 7 and 8.

Dividing the equations 7 and 8 by the unit cell length L , average axial forces and moments per unit length along the boundary of the equivalent plate can be found.

$$N_x = \frac{\bar{N}_x}{L} = \frac{(EA)^*}{L} \mathbf{e}_x^o + d \frac{(EA)^*}{L} \mathbf{k}_x \quad (\text{Eq. 9})$$

$$N_y = \frac{\bar{N}_y}{L} = \frac{(EA)^*}{L} \mathbf{e}_y^o - d \frac{(EA)^*}{L} \mathbf{k}_y$$

$$M_x = \frac{\bar{M}_x}{L} = d \frac{(EA)^*}{L} \mathbf{e}_x^o + \left(\frac{(EI)^*}{L} + d^2 \frac{(EA)^*}{L} \right) \mathbf{k}_x \quad (\text{Eq. 10})$$

$$M_y = \frac{\bar{M}_y}{L} = -d \frac{(EA)^*}{L} \mathbf{e}_y^o + \left(\frac{(EI)^*}{L} + d^2 \frac{(EA)^*}{L} \right) \mathbf{k}_y$$

From equations 9 and 10, the equivalent A , B , and D matrices are

$$[A]_{icg}^{on} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{(EA)^*}{L} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{(EA)^*}{L} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{Eq. 11})$$

$$[B]_{icg}^{on} = \begin{bmatrix} d \frac{(EA)^*}{L} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -d \frac{(EA)^*}{L} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{Eq. 12})$$

$$[D]_{icg}^{on} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{(EI)^*}{L} + d^2 \frac{(EA)^*}{L} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{(EI)^*}{L} + d^2 \frac{(EA)^*}{L} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{Eq. 13})$$

Note that there are no Poisson coupling, and the x and y direction beams are completely separate. Also, note that the total stiffness ABD matrix is singular due to zero in-plane shear stiffness, A_{ss} , and twisting stiffness, D_{ss} , in equation 11 and 13. The in-plane shear stiffness A_{ss} is zero because the joints are assumed to behave as hinges and have no resistance to the rotation in the plane of the grid panel. For analysis purposes, A_{ss} is set to a small number on the order of 10^{-6} of A_{xx} . The twisting stiffness D_{ss} can be added into equation 13 by considering torsional rigidity of beams.

The twisting stiffness D_{ss} , the relation between the twisting moment M_s and the twisting curvature k_s , is formulated. The formulation is done by considering the torsional rigidity of

the T-section beam and the twisting rigidity of the equivalent plate. Fig. 10 shows the positive torsion or twisting moment and rotations for beams and plates.

Fig. 10 (a) Positive torsion and rotation for beams and (b) positive twisting moment and rotation for a plate

The beam torsion (T) and the twisting moment (M_s) of the equivalent plate are related as shown in eq. 14.

$$\begin{aligned} T_x &= (GJ)_x \frac{d\mathbf{q}_x}{dx} & T_y &= (GJ)_y \frac{d\mathbf{q}_y}{dy} \\ M_{xy} &= -\frac{T_x}{L} = -\frac{(GJ)_x}{L} \frac{d\mathbf{q}_x}{dx} & M_{yx} &= \frac{T_y}{L} = \frac{(GJ)_y}{L} \frac{d\mathbf{q}_y}{dy} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{Eq. 14})$$

where, the torsional rigidities of the beams are

$$(GJ)_x = (GJ)_y = (GJ) = \frac{1}{3} G_{rib} (hb^3 + ct^3) \quad (\text{Eq. 15})$$

From the force equilibrium, twisting moments M_{xy} and M_{yx} are equal (eq. 16).

$$M_{xy} = M_{yx} = M_s \quad (\text{Eq. 16})$$

The twisting curvature k_s of the equivalent plate and beam rotation angle \mathbf{q} are related as follows:

$$k_s = -\left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{f}_y}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}_x}{\partial y} \right) = -\frac{d\mathbf{q}_x}{dx} + \frac{d\mathbf{q}_y}{dy} \quad (\text{Eq. 17})$$

From the equations 14 to 17, D_{ss} can be written in terms of rib material properties and the dimensions of the rib and cap as in eq. 18:

$$D_{ss} = \frac{(GJ)}{2L} = \frac{G_{rib} (hb^3 + ct^3)}{6L} \quad (\text{Eq. 18})$$

Usually, D_{ss} is negligible compared to D_{xx} or D_{yy} since the torsional rigidity of a tall open section beam is much smaller than the bending rigidity. For the preliminary design, the twisting stiffness can be neglected.

The out-of-plane shear stiffness matrix H is derived from the transverse shear rigidity of the T-beam. It is assumed that the shear is carried by the rib only and the shear rigidity (GA) is shown in eq. 19.

$$(GA) = G_{rib}bh \quad (\text{Eq. 19})$$

The average transverse shear force per unit length along the boundary of the equivalent plate are shown in eq. 20 where the shear correction factor, \mathbf{a} , of 5/7 is used.

$$V_x = \mathbf{a} \frac{(GA)}{L} \mathbf{e}_{xz} \quad (\text{Eq. 20})$$

$$V_y = \mathbf{a} \frac{(GA)}{L} \mathbf{e}_{yz}$$

Hence the H matrix in local x-y-z coordinate is

$$[H]_{icg}^{on} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{a} \frac{(GA)}{L} & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{a} \frac{(GA)}{L} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{Eq. 21})$$

In this section, the equivalent stiffness matrices for a flat square ICG have been formulated. It is easily extendible to more general rectangular grids. The effect of slots is integrated into the formulation in terms of the cap efficiency factors. The effects of the slots on the twisting rigidity D_{ss} and the out-of plane shear stiffness terms H_{xx} and H_{yy} are neglected because these terms are relatively small for grid configurations with tall unidirectional ribs. The singularity of the ABD matrix of an ICG due to the zero in-plane shear stiffness A_{ss} is not recoverable due to the joint configuration of the ICG. Although the in-plane shear stiffness of an ICG is practically zero, the grid has many applications where shear loading is negligible. For analysis with a finite element package, a small number is assigned for A_{ss} to avoid the singularity. When skins or internal ribs are added, the stiffness matrix becomes non-singular. The stiffness of the skins and the internal ribs can be added to the stiffness of the ICG using the principle of superposition.

CONCLUSION

The simple and cost effective manufacturing and assembly process for the rectangular grids have been developed. The stiffness behavior of the grid can be predicted accurately by the equivalent stiffness models developed in this study.

Composite grids represent a revolutionary class of structures. There has not been anything comparable. They are generic and can lead to many applications having large and small, multi-functional structures.

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